

Geological Setting

**Characterisation of the
saline aquifer reservoir
complex and surrounding
areas of the Lusitanian
Basin for offshore CO₂
storage in Portugal**

Prepared by

**Rui Veloso and Pedro
Madureira**

Report developed under
MoTech Project

Contents

1.	Introduction	5
2.	Available dataset.....	6
3.	Geological setting of the Lusitanian Basin and CO ₂ storage reservoir complex...8	
3.1	Area of interest and its context.....	8
3.2	Stratigraphy, tectonic evolution and basin architecture.....	9
4.	CO ₂ Storage Complex.....	16
4.1	Late Triassic to Early Jurassic (~237 – 174 Ma).....	16
4.1.1	Torres Vedras Group (Aptian-Albian boundary)	16
4.1.2	Coimbra Formation (Sinemurian, ~195 Ma).....	18
4.1.3	Brenha Formation (Pliensbachian–Callovian, ~160 Ma).....	18
4.2	Late Jurassic to Early Cretaceous (Valanginian–Aptian, ~139 – 113 Ma) 18	
4.3	Early Cretaceous Lithospheric Breakup (~113 – 100.5 Ma).....	18
4.3.1	Albian to Turonian (~113.0 – 93.9 Ma)	18
4.3.2	Cacém Formation (Cenomanian–Turonian, ~100.5 – 89.8 Ma).....	18
4.4	Late Cretaceous (~100.5 – 66 Ma)	19
4.5	Cenozoic (~66 Ma – Present)	19
5.	Well log analysis and seismics interpretation.....	20
5.1	Log analysis and petrophysics.....	20
5.2	Seismic horizon and fault interpretation.....	20
5.3	Trap characterisation	22
5.4	Location and geometry	22
5.5	Risk assessment:.....	24
5.6	Summary on the structural integrity of the storage complex.....	25
6.	Future Perspectives.....	27
6.1	Scenarios.....	27
6.2	Techno-economic description (actions, schedule and costs).....	28

6.3	Transport options.....	31
6.4	Economic results and priority.....	33
6.5	Final development selection.....	34
7.	References	37

Acronym Index

Cacém Formation (CF)

Capital Expenditure (CAPEX)

Carbon Capture, Utilization and Storage (CCUS)

Effective Porosity (PHIE)

Greenhouse Gas (GHG)

Health, Safety, and Environmental (HSE)

Lusitanian Basin (LB)

Measurement, Monitoring, and Verification (MMV)

Million tonnes (Mt)

Million years (Ma)

National Energy and Climate Plan (PNEC 2030)

National Strategy for Hydrogen (EN-H2)

To Be Defined (TBD)

Torres Vedras Group (TVG)

West Iberian Margin (WIM)

1. Introduction

The National Energy and Climate Plan (PNEC 2030) was first introduced in 2019, setting the strategic framework to achieve carbon neutrality by 2050. The plan was revised in 2024, where more ambitious targets for the reduction of greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions were defined. It now aims for a 55% reduction in GHG emissions by 2030 compared to 2005 levels (~75 Mt) and accelerates the goal of achieving carbon neutrality until 2045 instead of 2050. Moreover, in the revised PNEC 2030, Carbon Capture, Utilization and Storage (CCUS) is mentioned as an essential technology to help Portugal meet its decarbonisation targets in hard-to-abate industries where reducing emissions is challenging (e.g. Cement) and where other forms of decarbonization might be more difficult or less effective. The plan also emphasizes the need for innovation and investment in CCUS, pointing to the need for research and development to improve the efficiency and cost-effectiveness of these technologies and to plan the necessary infrastructure. Furthermore, CO₂ utilization may foster the production of low-carbon hydrogen and other sustainable fuels.

The National Strategy for Hydrogen (EN-H2) projects that from 2025 onwards, CCUS will be an important technology to assist the conversion of green hydrogen into synthetic methane and aviation fuels, with an estimated CO₂ demand of 1 Mt per year by 2030. Consequently, CCUS is now regarded as a key enabler of Portugal's energy transition (DGEG, 2020).

In this context, the Lusitanian Basin (LB) in Portugal has been identified as a promising site for CO₂ storage, with detailed geological characterisation performed under the PilotSTRATEGY project. The selected site is located in the offshore sector of the northern LB, where extensive seismic and (legacy) well data analyses have confirmed its suitability for CCUS applications. This document focuses on the geological setting and characterisation of the saline aquifer that may constitute the future storage reservoir and its surrounding areas, integrating sedimentological, petrophysical, and structural data and information to assess its potential.

2. Available dataset

The dataset for the seismic interpretation of the LB offshore area is illustrated in Figure 1. It includes the 3D Cabo Mondego & São Pedro de Moel seismic volume, several 2D seismic profiles, and ten offshore wells used to correlate with the seismic data. The main area of interest, outlined by a solid black line, focuses on offshore exploration, though some onshore analysis was conducted, particularly on three petroleum exploration wells to enhance the understanding of the offshore storage complex.

Figure 1 - Dataset used for the offshore area subsurface geological characterisation. Retrieved from Silva et al. (2023).

For well log analysis and petrophysical evaluation, 12 vertical wells (7 offshore, 5 onshore) were considered (Figure 2). These wells, drilled mainly for petroleum exploration, date back to the 1970s (offshore), except for the onshore wells: Alc-1 (2012), MRW-5, MRW-8, and MRW-9 (1960s), and Alj-2 (1990s). Due to their age, information on data acquisition is limited, and borehole quality is generally poor, with washouts affecting key formations. The dataset also includes rock samples from the Torres Vedras

Group (the most promising reservoir for CO₂ storage), Alcobaça Formation, and Cacém Formation (primary seal), collected onshore for mineralogical, petrographic, petrophysical, and geomechanical analyses.

Figure 2 - Basemap of the study area illustrating the location of the wells (highlighted in red) that were included in the petrophysical analysis. Retrieved from Silva et al. (2023).

3. Geological setting of the Lusitanian Basin and CO₂ storage reservoir complex

3.1 Area of interest and its context

The study area is located in the offshore northern sector of the LB, along the Atlantic western coast of Portugal, as presented in Figure 3. The LB is a Meso-Cenozoic rift basin that evolved through multiple rifting episodes during the Mesozoic. The basin's evolution began in the Late Triassic–Early Jurassic (~237-174 Ma) with the first rifting event, followed by two additional rifting phases in the Late Jurassic and Early Cretaceous, culminating in continental break-up between the Early and Late Cretaceous. Sedimentation alternated between continental and marine influences, with siliciclastic and carbonate deposits being predominant.

The offshore study area is delineated in the enlarged area of Figure 3, showing the depth structural map of the Torres Vedras Group (TVG), the primary reservoir unit for CO₂ storage, interpreted within the 3D seismic volume Cabo Mondego & São Pedro de Moel. The map highlights the major fault structures influencing reservoir geometry and continuity.

Figure 3 - Location of the study area in the offshore of the Portuguese coast (north of Lusitanian Basin). The image shows the depth structural map of Torres Vedras Group (reservoir for future CO₂ storage), interpreted within the 3D seismic volume Cabo Mondego and S. Pedro de Moel, highlighting some of the main faults identified in the region. Retrieved from Silva et al. (2023).

3.2 Stratigraphy, tectonic evolution and basin architecture

The LB evolved as a result of multiple rifting episodes, leading to its present-day structural configuration. The basin is composed of a series of diapir-bound and fault-bound sub-basins, developed on a horst-graben anisotropic basement fabric, controlled by Late Hercynian NNE-SSW and NW-SE strike-slip faults, which were reactivated as normal faults with the onset of intracontinental rifting during the Late Triassic (Wilson et al., 1989; Pinheiro et al., 1996; Rasmussen et al., 1998). A simplified stratigraphic chart (Figure 4) illustrates the tectono-sedimentary packages deposited throughout the Mesozoic. The tectonic evolution of the LB is marked by three to four main rifting episodes, recorded in both the Lusitanian and neighbouring Porto Basin (Wilson et al., 1989; Pinheiro et al., 1996; Stapel et al., 1996; Leinfelder & Wilson, 1998; Rasmussen et al., 1998; Alves et al., 2003; Alves & Cunha, 2018):

1. Rift 1a (Late Triassic) and Rift 1b (Early Jurassic) (1a: ~237-201 Ma and 1b: ~201-174 Ma) – Initial intracontinental rifting leading to evaporite deposition (Dagorda Salt Unit) and the formation of early sub-basins.

2. Rift 2 (Late Oxfordian–Berriasian) (~163-139 Ma) – Increased subsidence and extension, reactivating deep-seated basement faults and further developing the structural framework.
3. Rift 3 (Valanginian/Hauterivian – Aptian) (~139-113 Ma) – Final rifting stage in the continental-slope basins west of the LB, with significant crustal thinning, leading up to lithospheric breakup.

The LB's structural framework developed as a result of these major rifting events, each contributing to the basin's present-day architecture. The first rifting phase (Late Triassic–Early Jurassic) initiated basin formation, marked by evaporite deposition, including the Dagorda Salt Unit (Hettangian, ~199 Ma). This unit would later play a critical role in controlling structural traps and influencing salt tectonics. A period of angular unconformity during the Callovian marked a key tectono-eustatic shift, followed by renewed rifting activity extending into the Early Cretaceous. The reactivation of deep-seated basement faults, the erosion of uplifted rift shoulders, and the deposition of transitional carbonate and siliciclastic sediments also occur during this period. The Aptian-Albian interval represents the final lithospheric breakup phase, leading to continental separation and the establishment of an open-marine environment.

Figure 4 - Simplified lithostratigraphic chart of the Lusitanian Basin (adapted from Casacão et al., 2023), including the main tectonic events that impacted the basin's evolution. Here it is highlighted the storage complex play that is being considered, formed by the Torres Vedras Group (reservoir for future CO₂ storage) and Cacém Formation (seal), and the secondary seal formed by the Aveiro Group (Carapau, Gândara and Dourada formations). Retrieved from Silva et al. (2023).

During the Cenozoic basin inversion, post-Hercynian faults were reactivated, leading to complex interactions between compressional forces and pre-existing Hettangian evaporites. These thick salt deposits responded to compressional stresses by mobilizing and rejuvenating salt diapirs, which significantly influenced the structural evolution of the basin (Ribeiro et al., 1990; Wilson et al., 1989; Pinheiro et al., 1996; Alves et al., 2002).

The interaction between salt diapirism and deep basement faulting has played a fundamental role in the structural evolution of the LB, particularly during the Jurassic extensional phases (Zbyszewski, 1959; Wilson et al., 1989; Ribeiro et al., 1990; Pinheiro et al., 1996; Rasmussen et al., 1998; Alves et al., 2002). One of the clearest manifestations of this relationship is the inflation of salt pillows atop relative footwalls and basement highs, controlled by Late Hercynian lineaments. These structures were accompanied by salt withdrawal from subsident hanging walls, leading to the development of broad sub-basins, where sediment accumulation was strongly influenced by fault reactivation.

During the Late Jurassic, fault-controlled subsidence was at its peak, triggering widespread salt movement and facilitating the formation of several sub-basins across the LB. These include the Arruda, Turcifal, Bombarral-Alcobaça, and Consolação sub-basins in the central sector, as well as the Monte Real, Rio Maior, Pombal, Cabo Mondego, and São Pedro de Moel sub-basins in the northern sector, as illustrated in Figure 5. This extensive faulting and diapirism resulted in a highly compartmentalized stratigraphic framework, which would later influence hydrocarbon exploration and potential CO₂ storage feasibility.

Figure 5 - Location of the main sub-basins and salt diapirs in the Central/Northern sectors of the Lusitanian Basin (adapted from Casacão et al., 2023). The red dashed line delineates the location of the offshore study area. Retrieved from Silva et al. (2023).

Following this period of tectonic activity, sedimentation continued into the Lower Cretaceous, leading to the deposition of a thick sequence of fluvial-deltaic siliciclastic deposits, primarily sourced from the uplifted hinterland to the east. This unit, corresponds to the TVG, and is regarded as one of the most significant reservoir targets in hydrocarbon exploration across the West Iberian Margin (WIM). Seismic interpretation confirms the extent and continuity of this seismic-stratigraphic unit, with well penetrations in the study area providing further validation. However, the thickness and lithological variability of the TVG were significantly affected by salt diapirism, which dictated sediment transport pathways and localized accommodation space. Two primary types of salt-related structures have been identified within the study area:

- Salt pillows, which remained relatively shallow and did not fully pierce into overlying formations of the Late Jurassic succession;
- Inflated salt diapirs, which were subsequently reactivated and bounded by elongated reverse faults during the Miocene inversion phase. These features were intersected by exploration wells, including “Espadarte” (14A-1, 14A-2) and “Sardinha” (13E-1, 13C-1).

As crustal stretching continued into the Early Cretaceous, a basin-ward migration of the rift locus was recorded (Murillas et al., 1990; Alves et al., 2009). This shift was primarily driven by continental crust thinning and rupture, culminating in the Upper Barremian, followed by progressive mantle exhumation and thinning up to the Aptian-Albian boundary (Soares et al., 2012). The final stages of rifting ultimately led to lithospheric breakup, marking the onset of seafloor spreading between the WIM and the Canadian Grand Banks by the Late Aptian (Pinheiro et al., 1996). The Albian–Cenomanian/Turonian sequence represents the final breakup phase, deposited above the Aptian breakup unconformity, which is particularly well preserved in the LB.

With the completion of continental breakup, the West Iberian Margin transitioned into the continental drift stage, characterized by the deposition of evolving siliciclastics in the northern LB, while the southern LB remained largely emerged. Notably, unlike the southern sector, the study area exhibits minimal evidence of the widespread Late Cretaceous magmatic episode (Miranda et al., 2009; Pereira et al., 2020) that preceded Cenozoic uplift and inversion.

The Cenozoic tectonic evolution of the LB was dominated by compressional events linked to the Alpine orogeny (Terrinha et al., 2019). Two significant inversion events reshaped the basin:

- The Pyrenean Phase (Eocene), associated with broad regional uplift and fault reactivation.
- The Betic Phase (Miocene), marked by significant compressional deformation, which intensified salt diapirism, resulting in the present structural configuration of the basin.

The geometry and structural configuration of the study area can be summarized in a seismic cross-section (Figure 6), where the main storage complex elements are highlighted.

Figure 6 - Structural configuration of the study area, resulting from the interpretation of an E-W seismic line. Main storage elements comprise the Torres Vedras Group (primary reservoir for future CO₂ storage), the Cacém & Aveiro units (primary and secondary seals) and the Alcobaça Formation (secondary reservoir target). It is also interpreted the Dagorda salt unit (in pink), and the impact of diapirism in the creation of anticlines (structural traps). Retrieved from Silva et al. (2023).

4. CO₂ Storage Complex

The LB exhibits a well-defined Meso-Cenozoic stratigraphic succession, with sedimentation driven by rift-related subsidence, salt movement, and eustatic fluctuations. Two potential units for CO₂ storage have been identified, but recent geological re-evaluations and new interpretations have favoured the Cretaceous one over its Triassic-Lower Jurassic counterpart.

4.1 Lower Cretaceous (~145 – 100.5 Ma)

4.1.1 Torres Vedras Group (Aptian-Albian boundary)

The Torres Vedras Group represents a siliciclastic succession deposited in fluvial to deltaic environments, forming part of the post-rift sedimentary infill during the later stages of lithospheric breakup between the West Iberian Margin (WIM) and the Canadian Grand Banks (Pinheiro et al., 1996; Dinis et al., 2008). This unit, illustrated in Figure 5, is characterized by coarse to fine-grained sandstones interbedded with siltstones and clays, reflecting alternating high-energy fluvial channels and lower-energy deltaic plains (Wilson et al., 1989; Rey et al., 2006). When characterising TVG it's important to note the following aspects.

Porosity & Permeability:

The TVG exhibits average porosities around 20% (Table 1), with permeability enhanced by well-sorted grain sizes and minimal clay matrix, making it the most promising CO₂ storage unit in the LB.

Table 1 - Summary with final petrophysical results, per well (*non-reliable result – only based on Neutron log). Retrieved from Silva et al. (2023).

	Well Name	WD (m)	Top (MD m)	Bottom (MD m)	Gross (m)	Net (m)	N/G (%)	Av Phi (%)
TORRES VEDRAS FM.	Do-1C	84	880	1238	358	289	81	19
	Mo-1	45	703	1024	321	262	82	23
	13C-1	83	412	761	349	37	11	19
	13E-1	129	356	748	392	114	29	22
	14C-1A	133	802	1062	280	70	27	22
	Fa-1	112	860	1300	440	109	25	17
	16A-1	125	974	1472	498	320	64	17
SILVES Grp.	Do-1C	84	3525	3668	141	0.5	0.3	10
	13C-1	83	2459	2737	278	0.3	0.1	12
	Fa-1	112	2065	2597	532	1.4	0.3	9
	Alc-1	-	2653	3240	587	10.4	1.8	10
	Alj-2	-	3027	3616	589	-	-	-
Alcobaça	MRW-5	-	778	1084	306	305	99*	18*

Seismic Expression:

Transparent to high-amplitude continuous seismic facies correlate with sandstone-dominated intervals, while discontinuous reflectors mark finer-grained interbeds (Dinis et al., 2008). Lateral variability in sand packages complicates well correlation but underscores the unit's heterogeneous yet laterally extensive reservoir potential.

Depositional Controls:

Fluvial systems were influenced by rift-related subsidence and hinterland uplift, while deltaic sedimentation responded to episodic marine transgressions during the Early Cretaceous (Leinfelder & Wilson, 1989; Azerêdo et al., 2003).

Stratigraphic Context:

The TVG is stratigraphically overlain by the Cacém Formation (Cenomanian–Turonian carbonates), which acts as a regional seal (Witt, 1977). Its position within the Early Cretaceous syn-rift to post-rift transition ensures burial depths sufficient for supercritical CO₂ storage, while its marls and evaporites composition minimises geochemical reactivity risks.

4.1.2 Coimbra Formation (Sinemurian, ~195 Ma)

Marked by the onset of marine incursion with dolomites as presented by (Azerêdo et al., 2003) distinguishes by its strong seismic reflector at the top, facilitating regional correlation and distinguishing it from the underlying chaotic Dagorda facies.

4.1.3 Brenha Formation (Pliensbachian–Callovian, ~160 Ma)

- Consists of marlstones, limestones, and marly limestones deposited in open marine to shelf environments (Witt, 1977).
- Reflects prolonged carbonate-dominated sedimentation interrupted by tectono-eustatic controls linked to North Atlantic basin evolution (Terrinha et al., 2019b).

4.2 Late Jurassic to Early Cretaceous (Valanginian–Aptian, ~139 – 113 Ma)

Post-Callovian extension reactivated basement faults, driving erosion of rift shoulders and deposition of:

- **Cabaços Formation:** Transitional carbonates marking initial marine flooding.
- **Montejunto Formation:** Open-marine limestones indicative of stable platform conditions.
- **Abadia & Lourinhã formations:** Fluvio-deltaic to turbiditic siliciclastics, reflecting syn-rift subsidence and hinterland uplift (Leinfelder & Wilson, 1989; Pena dos Reis, 2000; Azerêdo et al., 2003).

4.3 Early Cretaceous Lithospheric Breakup (~113 – 100.5 Ma)

4.3.1 Albian to Turonian (~113.0 – 93.9 Ma)

Fluvial Systems:

Albian–Cenomanian fluvial deposits dominate the northern LB, influenced by rift-related topography (Wilson et al., 1989; Rey et al., 2006).

4.3.2 Cacém Formation (Cenomanian–Turonian, ~100.5 – 89.8 Ma)

- Shallow-marine carbonates deposited during a major transgression, forming the regional seal for the TVG (Witt, 1977).

- **Outcrop examples** (Figure 7): illustrates seismic interpretations at smaller scale similar to the lithological complexity, interbedding patterns, and thickness variations observed in subsurface well data.

Figure 7 - Sedimentary patterns of the Torres Vedras Group (location: Pedras d'el Rey beach). Retrieved from Silva et al. (2023).

4.4 Late Cretaceous (~100.5 – 66 Ma)

Sedimentation:

Predominantly fluvial, with episodic marine incursions (early Turonian, Coniacian, Campanian, Maastrichtian) linked to eustatic rises.

Magmatism:

Regional alkaline intrusions affected WIM basins but are absent in the study area.

4.5 Cenozoic (~66 Ma – Present)

Inversion Events:

Two major phases (Ribeiro et al., 1990) reshaped basin architecture, influencing deposition of:

- Shallow marine to deltaic sediments: Sandstones, conglomerates, and clays.
- Alluvial deposits: Coarse-grained fluvial systems interbedded with fine-grained floodplain clays.

5. Well log analysis and seismics interpretation

In order to characterise the subsurface of the Lusitanian Basin. Well data was used to evaluate reservoir properties, while seismic surveys enabled the mapping of key stratigraphic horizons and structural features. The integration of these datasets provides insights into reservoir potential, structural traps, and geological constraints relevant to CO₂ storage. Note that Figure 4 serves as illustrative to understand the previously mention structure from the Silves Group to Moreia.

5.1 Log analysis and petrophysics

Twelve vertical wells (7 offshore, 5 onshore), drilled between the 1960s and 2012 (Figure 2), were analysed. Data limitations included poor hole quality (evidenced by caliper log-identified washouts), absence of core calibration, and lack of image logs, hindering sedimentary environment and stress characterisation. Cut-offs for effective porosity (PHIE) defined reservoir (PHIE >8%) and seal (PHIE <2%) intervals. Key findings:

- Torres Vedras Group (Early Cretaceous): High average porosity (20%) and variable N/G ratios support its role as the primary reservoir (Table 1). Lateral variability in sand packages complicates well correlation.
- Alcobaça Formation (Late Jurassic): Limited to MRW-5 well data; insufficient for robust assessment, leading to its dismissal as a viable target.

5.2 Seismic horizon and fault interpretation

A combination of 2D (2,950 km of legacy data, 1973–1984) and 3D seismic volumes (Cabo Mondego and São Pedro de Moel, 2011) was used (Figure 1). Six key horizons were mapped (Figure 8): Top Alcobaça Formation (~145 Ma), Top Torres Vedras Group (~100 Ma), Top Cacém Formation (93 Ma), Top Aveiro Group (~68 Ma), Top Espadarte Formation (50 Ma) and Seabed (0 Ma).

Figure 8 - Lithostratigraphic chart of the Lusitanian Basin, its main tectono-stratigraphic units and a seismic screenshot with the main horizons that were mapped (Seabed, Top Espadarte, Top Aveiro Group, Top Cacém, Top Torres Vedras, and Top Alcobaça). Retrieved from Silva et al. (2023).

Some of the structures that were identified were:

- **Synclines:** Dismissed due to risks related with migration of the CO₂ plume.
- **Anticlines:** Promising targets in deeper western offshore areas, though shallow anticlines were excluded to ensure supercritical CO₂ phase stability.

Fault interpretation identified 24 faults (predominantly N-S/NW-SE-striking normal faults; throws from tens to hundreds of metres). Reverse faults linked to halokinesis (salt tectonics) created structural highs. Faults delineation in western zones exhibited higher uncertainty due to sparse 2D coverage.

Time-Depth Conversion:

Interval velocities from well data (Table 2) informed the seismic velocity model. Discrepancies (~20 m for TVG/CF tops) arose from velocity uncertainties and horizon-picking inaccuracies. Legacy 3D migration velocity models were discarded due to geologically implausible depth maps. Final interval velocities ranged from 1,650 m/s (Seabed) to 4,300 m/s (Table 2).

Table 2 - Summary of the interval velocities (m/s) considered for each interpreted unit. Retrieved from Silva et al. (2023).

Seismic Horizons	Interval Velocity (m/s)
Seabed	16500
Espadarte Formation	2200
Aveiro Group	2650
Cacém Formation	4300
Torres Vedras Group	3350
Alcobaça Formation	3600

5.3 Trap characterisation

As mentioned before, the characterisation of the trap within the complex was focused on identifying structural and stratigraphic closures suitable for CO₂ storage, prioritising sites with robust containment potential through an integrated approach combining seismic interpretation, well data, and petrophysical analysis. Structural traps were evaluated as 4-way dip closures, 3-way fault-dependent closures, and 2-way fault- or salt-bounded closures, considering seismic attributes to map fault geometries and salt diapir boundaries. Stratigraphic traps were identified via pinch-outs and lateral facies variations within the TVG reservoir, observed through seismic amplitude anomalies and well-log correlations. Hybrid traps, combining structural and stratigraphic elements, included salt-related anticlines with lateral facies changes, where diapirism influenced both structural uplift and sediment distribution. This multi-faceted analysis ensured a comprehensive assessment of trapping mechanisms, emphasizing containment reliability for CO₂ storage.

Key Prospect: Q4-TV1

5.4 Location and geometry

Located in the northern offshore study area, adjacent to the Do-1C well (Figures 13).

Figure 9 - Location and outline definition of the Q4-TV1 prospect and P10-P50-P90 closures (red outlines). The NE-SW and E-W 2D seismic sections (dashed purple lines) are illustrated in Figure 20 and Figure 25, respectively. Retrieved from Silva et al. (2023).

A 4-way dip closure with a subtle anticlinal structure, oriented N-S, covering ~25 km² (P50 scenario) to 250 km² (P10 scenario). Gross TVG thickness ranges from 30 m (P50) to 70 m (P10), with reservoir depths between 770–1238 m below seabed.

Structural Controls:

Bounded by N-S/NW-SE normal faults with throws of tens to hundreds of meters (Figure 14).

Figure 10 - E-W seismic section crossing the selected prospect Q4-TV1 (highlighted in red) and illustrating the identification of P10 and P50 closures. Retrieved from Silva et al. (2023).

Faults intersect the CF seal but show no evidence of post-Cretaceous reactivation, indicating possible seal integrity. TVG thins northward toward the Ca-1 well, indicating potential stratigraphic pinch-outs. Seismic amplitude anomalies suggest lateral facies changes from fluvial sandstones to deltaic shales.

5.5 Risk assessment:

The safe and effective storage of CO₂ in geological formations depends on multiple factors, including the integrity of the reservoir and caprock, fault behaviour, and subsurface pressure conditions. A thorough risk assessment is essential to identify potential challenges that could impact storage security and to develop appropriate mitigation strategies.

Primary Risks: Uncertain fault seal efficiency, limited well control on fault transmissivity, and shallow anticlinal crests (<500 m depth) risking CO₂ phase stability.

Mitigation: Prioritised deeper closures (>800 m) to ensure supercritical CO₂ conditions.

In addition to the primary risks, further challenges include uncertainty in how faults might allow CO₂ to move and variations in rock layers that could affect its migration. The limited well data in key faulted areas makes it difficult to confirm whether these structures can fully seal the CO₂. Additionally, thin rock layers that act as traps may have irregularities that could create potential leakage pathways. To address these risks, additional seismic data will be used to improve the structural models, and computer simulations have been done to predict how CO₂ will behave when injected. By selecting deeper storage sites with strong caprock layers, the project aims to reduce the risks of CO₂ leakage or changing phase.

5.6 Summary on the structural integrity of the storage complex

The selected storage complex for modelling comprises multiple stratigraphic units, each playing a critical role in defining the geological framework necessary for CO₂ storage. The key components include:

Main Reservoir: TVG, deposited during the Late Aptian to Cenomanian, represents the primary CO₂ storage unit. It is characterized by:

- Fluvial sandstones, interbedded with sealing clay layers.
- Reservoir depths ranging from 500m to 1000m, as confirmed by well data.
- Sedimentary fairways influenced by salt tectonics, affecting deposition patterns.
- Structural and stratigraphic trapping mechanisms, which enhance CO₂ containment potential.

Primary Seal: The CF serves as the primary sealing unit, providing an impermeable barrier above the main reservoir. This thick Upper Cretaceous formation consists of:

- Limestone and dolomite in the upper section, indicative of a marine carbonate platform.
- Marls and clays at the base, enhancing its sealing capacity.
- Notably, salt diapirism has had no significant impact on CF deposition, as evidenced by the uniform thickness observed in geological maps.

Overburden: Composed of Late Cretaceous and Cenozoic sediments, which will be integrated into the static model. These include:

- Espadarte Formation – A fluvial/lacustrine unit containing dolomites, clays, and sandstones.

- Aveiro Group – A secondary seal composed of alternating sands and claystones, potentially adding additional containment security.

While not directly relevant for dynamic fluid flow simulations, these units are essential for geomechanical modelling in assessing the structural integrity of the storage complex. The comprehensive geological characterisation of the offshore northern Lusitanian Basin under the work that has been developed by the Évora University and currently within the PilotSTRATEGY project confirms its suitability as a candidate site for large-scale CO₂ storage (e.g. Pereira et al., 2021). This assessment integrates sedimentological, structural, petrophysical, and geophysical data to define a robust storage complex and evaluate its containment potential.

In conclusion, the LB's tectono-sedimentary history, coupled with its well-defined storage complex, positions it as a strategic asset to implement Portugal's strategy on energy transition. Continued characterisation and risk mitigation will be critical to advancing this site toward operational deployment.

6. Future Perspectives

A comparative techno-economic evaluation has been developed under the previous STRATEGY CCUS and currently ongoing PilotSTRATEGY projects, consisting of selected scenarios across multiple European promising CO₂ storage sites, aiming to identify the optimal strategy for each region. This section of the report describes the logistics envisaged to support the development of the CCUS technology in the short-term in Portugal. The preliminary economic evaluation that was developed under the PilotSTRATEGY project considers both pre-commercial (Pilot Phase or Phase I) and commercial (Phase II) stages, applying inflated and discounted cash-flow analysis over the project's full life cycle.

6.1 Scenarios

The baseline scenario for the Lusitanian Basin CCUS project, as defined in the Framing Sessions (Canteli et al., 2023), consists of two sequential injection phases:

- **Phase I (Pilot-Scale Injection):** Up to 100kt of cumulative CO₂ injection
- **Phase II (Commercial Injection):** Up to 0.5Mt/year over a 30-year period.

This framework was refined through workshops, follow-up meetings, and discussions with regional stakeholders. The project considers two injection scenarios:

- **Intermittent Injection:** CO₂ transported via train from local point sources to the Figueira da Foz port and posteriorly shipped and injected offshore.
- **Continuous Injection:** CO₂ transported from Figueira da Foz port and injected through a 23km offshore pipeline.

In the pilot phase, CO₂ sources are expected to come from nearby emitter industries, located at a distance up to 70km from the port of Figueira-da-Foz (StrategyCCUS, Figure 17).

Figure 11 - Location of the main local CO₂ emitters, previously identified in StrategyCCUS project (Mesquita et al., 2024).

StrategyCCUS also identified an annual CO₂ supply potential of 60–90kt and recommended railway and shipping transport as the most flexible and cost-effective options with minimal infrastructural impact. It should also be noted that a significant CAPEX reduction results from avoiding pipeline CO₂ transport in the pilot phase. The construction of an offshore pipeline would require the need to de-risk subsurface uncertainties and address existing regulatory gaps. Instead, shipping transport provides a practical solution for continuous injection without requiring permanent infrastructure in the project's early stages.

6.2 Techno-economic description (actions, schedule and costs)

As previously mentioned, the scenarios for the LB follow a two-phase structure, from a pilot demonstration (Phase I) to the commercial stage:

- **Pilot Phase (Pre-Commercial):** An exploratory stage to assess the feasibility of progressing to commercial-scale operations.
- **Commercial Phase:** Full-scale implementation based on insights gained from the pilot phase.

The costs for both phases are detailed here, with the pilot phase serving as a crucial step in determining the commercial phase's viability. As outlined in Canteli et al. (2024), several items were considered:

- Minimum cost approach.
- Social engagement, awareness, and local development.
- Regulatory gaps understanding and research.
- Schedule acceleration for pilot development.
- Enhancement of commercial development.
- Health, safety, and environmental (HSE) risk limitation and territorial impact reduction.

These items formed the basis for assessing viable project development strategies. Given the impact of such an industrial project set in mixed offshore and onshore, the team decided to narrow the development criteria down to subsurface and infrastructural critical components. Proper subsurface characterisation is essential to manage uncertainties, meet HSE requirements, and minimise facility-related costs.

The project also considers two key CO₂ transport options (Figure 18) for the pilot phase:

- Train to Figueira da Foz port & shipping to the storage site.
- Train to Figueira da Foz & offshore pipeline transport.

Figure 12 - Main offshore transport options considered from the Figueira da Foz port to the storage site. Retrieved from Canteli et al. (2025).

For the pilot phase, the first option allows for a cost-effective, flexible, and rapid deployment strategy to demonstrate technical feasibility. During the commercial phase, transport will be primarily by pipeline, onshore and offshore, ensuring higher transport efficiency and long-term operational reliability, with the possibility of ships being used for transport of CO₂ from the more distant CO₂ source south of Portugal.

6.3 Transport options in the pilot phase

Transport to Figueira da Foz

The project takes advantage of existing railway infrastructure at both capture and port facilities, making railway transport the most practical and cost-effective option. Key parameters include:

- **CO₂ Transport Conditions:** Liquefied at 6.6 bar and -50°C.
- **Train Capacity:** 4,000 tonnes per trip, with a round trip taking 12 hours (including loading/unloading).
- **Total CO₂ Transported:** 270 kt over three years (requiring a license extension after the first year due to the 100 kt legal limit for pilot demonstrations).

To streamline operations, CO₂ will be transported without requiring intermediate storage or reconditioning at Figueira da Foz. Train waggons may serve as temporary storage units or, alternatively, CO₂ may be directly loaded into ships.

Transport from Figueira da Foz to the Injection Well

The transport strategy must balance flexibility, cost, and adaptability to project uncertainties. Minimizing permanent infrastructure investments is key to reducing financial risk, especially given potential reservoir performance challenges.

Pipeline Transport

Technically feasible but costly during the pilot phase. Best suited for large-scale commercial operations (Phase II) rather than the pilot phase. Design would have to consider a required pipeline size for future 4.73 Mt/year (by 2050): 8–10 inches in diameter, imposing high CAPEX. A further operational challenge would be maintaining pressure/temperature for the low CO₂ flow rates in the pilot phase.

Ship Transport

Shipping presents a more flexible and cost-effective transport solution for the pilot phase. Ships are designed to match the train waggon capacity of 4,000 tonnes and can complete a round trip in approximately 80 hours. The CO₂ remains in a liquefied state at 6.6 bar and -50°C throughout transport, eliminating the need for reconditioning at Figueira da Foz. Additionally, direct unloading from train to ship removes the requirement for temporary storage at the port, streamlining operations. Offshore delivery

can be achieved either through direct injection from the ship into the well or by transferring the CO₂ to a floating platform equipped with conditioning facilities. However, a key challenge associated with this method is the high CAPEX required for acquiring a dedicated vessel; therefore, retrofitting or renting an existing ship is recommended for the pilot phase to reduce initial investment costs.

Injection during the Pilot Phase

The pilot phase has three main objectives:

- Improve the characterisation of the offshore CO₂ reservoir.
- Test CO₂ injection conditions.
- Assess caprock quality for long-term storage.

Additionally:

- **Injection Rate:** 90 kt/year, totalling 270 kt over three years.
- **Regulatory Limitation:** Portuguese law DL 60/2012 restricts CCUS projects to 100 kt without additional licensing. A license extension is required to continue beyond year one.

Scalability and Transition

The modular transport system is designed for a seamless shift from ship-based to pipeline transport as injection volumes increase, supporting long-term CCUS deployment.

6.4 Costs and priority

To evaluate the CAPEX of different transport chains, only transport from local emitters to Figueira da Foz port was considered. The capture and conditioning of CO₂ at the sources were not included in this assessment, though it was assumed that CO₂ would be transported at the highest purity and pressure levels.

Cost Assumptions and Transport Model

The techno-economic assumptions from (Myers et al., 2024) were used to estimate operating and financing costs for onshore liquid CO₂ transport (Table 5).

Table 3 - Physical Assumptions for Train Cost Model. Retrieved from Silva et al. (2023).

Scope	Cement plant	Glass plant
Average annual mass flow of CO ₂ transported (kt-CO ₂ /y)	30,000	60,000
Road distance (km)	65	55
Location	Souselas	Marinha Grande
Transport Mode	Railway	Railway
Container Type	Tanker/Waggon	Tanker/Waggon
Water content (ppm-mol)	0	0
CO ₂ Pressure (bar)	6.6	6.6
CO ₂ Temperature (°C)	-50	-50

CAPEX Estimations for Transport Chains

The preliminary estimates of CAPEX for railway, shipping, and pipeline transport are presented in Table 6, as a result from the PilotSTRATEGY project.

Table 4 - Estimated CAPEX of the transport chains for the Portuguese region (TBD – to be defined; Railway transport cost estimated from StrategyCCUS project). Retrieved from Silva et al. (2023).

Scope	Phase I – Pilot		Phase II – Commercial	
	Detail	Cost (M€)	Detail	Cost (M€)
Permitting	Guarantee transport licences (train + shipping)	0.2	Guarantee transport licence (train + pipeline)	0.2
	Liquified CO ₂ tanker	TBD	Liquified CO ₂ tanker	TBD
Infrastructure	Figueira da Foz port offloading/loading facilities	TBD	Figueira da Foz port offloading/loading facilities – high pressure shipping, requiring boundary station (post-metering at 70 bar) and	2.5

			temporary pressurized storage	
Railway (estimated in 2030)	Railway from Souselas and Marinha Grande industrial sources	10-20€/tonCO ₂	Railway from Souselas and Marinha Grande industrial sources	10-20€/tonCO ₂
Pipeline	Offshore pipeline (23 km, 8'')	N/A	Offshore pipeline (23 km, 8'')	20
Injection facility	Injection platform (no heavy subsea infrastructure)	TBD	Manifold & wellhead (incl. block valve module)	TBD

Transport Mode Selection by Project Phase

- **Phase I (Pilot Stage)** – The combination of railway & shipping is the preferred option due to its lower CAPEX, greater flexibility, and faster permitting process. This approach minimises the need for bulky surface infrastructure at the storage site and reduces environmental and administrative challenges.
- **Phase II (Commercial Stage)** – The offshore pipeline becomes the preferred transport mode, providing greater operational efficiency and long-term scalability.

Despite uncertainties in shipping feasibility and costs, railway and shipping transport offer the most viable approach for Phase I, while pipeline transport is prioritized for Phase II commercial injection, given its logistical and operational advantages.

6.5 Final development selection

The phased approach outlined for the CCUS project in the LB ensures a structured and adaptable development process, integrating permitting, well drilling & completion, transportation, and facilities construction alongside MMV (Measurement, Monitoring, and Verification) planning and execution.

Preliminary Development Schedule

The timeline (Figure 19) incorporates administrative and technical uncertainties for both the pilot/pre-commercial and commercial phases, considering key milestones:

- **Permitting & Authorities' Approval:** Essential for project initiation.
- **HSE Feasibility Studies:** Evaluating environmental and safety compliance.
- **Seismic Acquisition & Processing:** Required for subsurface characterisation.
- **Well Drilling & Completion:** Ensuring reservoir suitability for injection.

- **Transport Facilities Development:** Including train adaptation, long-lead items (e.g., cargo), and shipping vs. pipeline decisions.

Given expected delays in securing authority approvals and CO₂ transportation infrastructure, the pilot injection is projected to commence in Year 5.

Phase I – Pilot Injection Timeline

- **Years 1–2:** Seismic acquisition & processing.
- **Year 4:** Well drilling.
- **Year 5:** Start of pilot CO₂ injection.
- **Years 6–7:** 4D seismic acquisition to track plume evolution and de-risk subsurface uncertainties.

Phase II – Commercial Injection Timeline

- **End of Year 7:** Final Investment Decision (FID) for commercial-scale expansion.
- **Year 10:** Phase II injection begins, incorporating pipeline development for long-term scalability.

This phased structure enables a risk-managed, data-driven progression, ensuring the LB CCUS project evolves with technical, regulatory, and economic considerations at the forefront.

7. References

A

Alves, T., & Cunha, T. A. (2018). A phase of transient subsidence, sediment bypass and deposition of regressive–transgressive cycles during the breakup of Iberia and Newfoundland. *Earth and Planetary Science Letters*, 484, 168–183.

Alves, T., Gawthorpe, R. L., Hunt, D. H., & Monteiro, J. H. (2002). Jurassic tectono-sedimentary evolution of the Northern Lusitanian Basin (offshore Portugal). *Marine and Petroleum Geology*, 19(6), 727–754. DOI: [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0264-8172\(02\)00037-1](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0264-8172(02)00037-1)

Alves, T., Moita, C., Cunha, T., Ullnaess, M., Myklebust, R., Monteiro, J. H., & Manuppella, G. (2009). Diachronous evolution of Late Jurassic–Cretaceous continental rifting in the northeast Atlantic (west Iberian margin). *Tectonics*, 28(4), TC4003. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1029/2008TC002337>

Azerêdo, A. C., Duarte, L. V., Henriques, M. H., & Manuppella, G. (2003). Da dinâmica continental no Trásico aos mares do Jurássico Inferior e Médio. *Cadernos de Geologia de Portugal*. Instituto Geológico e Mineiro.

B

Benjumena, B., Garcia-Crespo, J., Mediato, J. F., Rey-Moral, C., Ayala, C., Rubio, F., Soto, R., Clariana, P., Pueyo, E. L., & Fernández-Cantell, P. (2022). Passive Seismic Methods as Support for the Interpretation of Legacy Seismic Profiles: CO₂ Storage. 83rd EAGE Annual Conference & Exhibition. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.3997/2214-4609.202210533>

C

Canteli, P., Garcia, D., Ron, M., Jannel, H., & Casacão, J. (2023). Deliverable 4.1 – Methodology for alternatives definition, prioritisation, and selection. PilotSTRATEGY project, Grant Agreement: 101022664.

Canteli, P., Moreno, I., Ron, M., Le Gallo, Y., Jannel, H., Casacão, J., Sliwinska, A., Tartars, E., Tyrologou, P., & Koukouzas, N. (2024). Deliverable 4.2 – Conceptual

scenarios definition to enable decision support. PilotSTRATEGY project, Grant Agreement: 101022664.

Canteli, P., Moreno, I., Ron, M., Le Gallo, Y., Casacão, J., Sliwinska, A., Krawczyk, P., Tartars, E., Ktenas, D., Tyrologou, P., Karatrantou, C., & Koukouzas, N. (2025). Deliverable 4.9 - Economic evaluation of alternatives and prioritisation results. PilotSTRATEGY project, Grant Agreement: 101022664.

Casacão, J., Silva, F., Rocha, J., Almeida, J., & Santos, M. (2023). Aspects of salt diapirism and structural evolution of Mesozoic–Cenozoic basins at the West Iberian margin. *AAPG Bulletin*, 107(1), 49–85. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1306/08072221100>

D

Davison, I., & Barreto, P. (2016). Deformation and sedimentation processes, and hydrocarbon accumulations on upturned salt diapir flanks in the Lusitanian Basin, Portugal. *Petroleum Geoscience*, 23(2), 138–156.

DGEG. (2020). Roadmap for Carbon Neutrality 2050 (RNC2050). Direção-Geral de Energia e Geologia.

Dinis, J. L., Rey, J., Cunha, P. P., Callapez, P., & Pena dos Reis, R. (2008). Stratigraphy and allogenic controls of the western Portugal Cretaceous: An updated synthesis. *Cretaceous Research*, 29(5–6), 772–780. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cretres.2008.05.027>

G

Gunn, P. J., Fitzgerald, D., Yassi, N., & Dart, P. (1997). New algorithms for visually enhancing airborne geophysical data. *Exploration Geophysics*, 28(2), 220–224.

L

Leinfelder, R. R., & Wilson, R. C. L. (1989). Third-order sequences in an Upper Jurassic rift-related second-order sequence, central Lusitanian Basin, Portugal. In P. C. Graciansky, J. Hardenbol, T. Jacquin, & P. R. Vail (Eds.), *Mesozoic and Cenozoic Sequence Stratigraphy of European Basins* (pp. 507–525). SEPM Special Publication.

M

Miranda, R., Valadares, V., Terrinha, P., Mata, J., Azevedo, M. D. R., Gaspar, M., Kullberg, J. C., & Ribeiro, C. (2009). Age constraints on the Late Cretaceous alkaline magmatism on the West Iberian Margin. *Cretaceous Research*, 30(5), 575–586.

Murillas, J., Mougnot, D., Boulot, G., Comas, M.C., Banda, E., & Mauffret, A., (1990). Structure and evolution of the Galicia Interior Basin (Atlantic western Iberian continental margin). *Tectonophysics*, 184, p. 297-319

P

Palain, C. (1976). Une série détritico terrigène, les “Grés de Silves”: Trias et Lias inférieur du Portugal. *Memórias dos Serviços Geológicos de Portugal*, 25, 377.

Pena dos Reis, R. (2000). Morfologias de talude instável em contexto de rifting. Exemplo do Jurássico superior da Bacia Lusitânica. *Ciências da Terra (UNL)*, 5, 65–68.

Pereira, P., Ribeiro, C., & Carneiro, J. (2022). Identification and characterisation of geological formations with CO₂ storage potential in Portugal. *Petroleum Geoscience*.

Pinheiro, L. M., Wilson, R. C. L., Reis, R. P., Whitmarsh, R. B., & Ribeiro, A. (1996). The western Iberian margin: A geophysical and geological overview. *Proceedings of the Ocean Drilling Program Scientific Results*, 149, 3–23.

R

Rasmussen, E. S., Lomholt, S., Andersen, C., & Velbaek, O. V. (1998). Aspects of the structural evolution of the Lusitanian Basin in Portugal and the shelf and slope area offshore Portugal. *Tectonophysics*, 300(1–4), 199–225.

Rey, J., Dinis, J. L., Callapez, P., & Cunha, P. P. (2006). Da rotura continental à margem passiva: Composição e evolução do Cretácico de Portugal. *Cadernos de Geologia de Portugal*, 75. Instituto Geológico e Mineiro.

Ribeiro, A., Kullberg, M. C., Kullberg, J. C., Manuppella, G., & Philipps, S. (1990). A review of Alpine tectonics in Portugal: Foreland detachment in basement and cover rocks. *Tectonophysics*, 184(3–4), 357–366. DOI: [https://doi.org/10.1016/0040-1951\(90\)90448-](https://doi.org/10.1016/0040-1951(90)90448-7)

7

S

Silva, D. M., Caeiro, M. H., Pereira, P., Ribeiro, C., Carneiro, J., Casacão, J., & Pina, B. (2023). Deliverable 2.7 - Geological Models Annex (Portugal). PilotSTRATEGY project, Grant Agreement: 101022664.

Soares, A. F., Kullberg, J. F., Bordalo da Rocha, R., & Callapez, P. M. (2012). Tectono-sedimentary model for the evolution of the Silves Group (Triassic, Lusitanian basin, Portugal). *Bulletin de la Société Géologique de France*, 183(3), 203–216.

Stapel, G., Cloetingh, S., & Pronk, B. (1996). Quantitative subsidence analysis of the Mesozoic evolution of the Lusitanian Basin (western Iberian margin). *Tectonophysics*, 266(1–4), 493–507.

T

Terrinha, P., Kullberg, J. C., & Ribeiro, C. (2019). The Alpine Orogeny in the West and Southwest Iberia Margins. In C. Quesada & J. Oliveira (Eds.), *The Geology of Iberia: A Geodynamic Approach* (pp. 253–283). Springer. DOI: https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-11295-0_11

W

Wilson, R. C. L., Hiscott, R. N., Willis, M. G., & Gradstein, F. M. (1989). The Lusitanian Basin of west-central Portugal: Mesozoic and Tertiary tectonic, stratigraphy, and subsidence history. In A. J. Tankard & H. R. Balkwill (Eds.), *Extensional Tectonics and Stratigraphy of the North Atlantic Margins* (Vol. 46, pp. 341–361). AAPG Memoir.

Witt, W. (1977). *Stratigraphy of the Lusitanian Basin*. Shell Prospex Portuguese Report (unpublished), 61.

Z

Zbyszewski, G. (1959). Étude structurale de la vallée typhonique de Caldas da Rainha (Portugal). *Memórias dos Serviços Geológicos de Portugal*, 3, 184.

Zhao, C., Zheng, Y., Wang, Y., & Zhao, L. (2022). Seismic ambient noise auto-correlation imaging in a CO₂ storage area. *Journal of Geophysics and Engineering*, 19, 1134–1148.